

Needs of citizen science educators and trainers

Report on a survey to identify needs of citizen science educators and trainers.

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The report is based on the responses from citizen science educators and trainers, for which we would like to thank.*

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Introduction

The European Citizen Science (ECS) project is a four year EU-funded project that started in August 2022 and will end in July 2026. It includes twenty-one organisations in total and is led by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA). The aim of the project is to widen and strengthen citizen science within Europe. It seeks to do so by strengthening the citizen science community, enhancing digital skills for FAIR (data which meet principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) and open science communities, developing the eu-citizen.science platform through co-design, developing the ECS Academy, boosting inclusion and diversity, advocating for citizen science and working on policy impact and investigation the impact of citizen science on research, society and economy.

This report focuses on identified needs of citizen science educators and trainers via a survey sent within the context of building up the European Citizen Science Academy (ECS Academy). A **citizen science educator and trainer** was defined for the purpose of the survey as an individual that provides both formal and/or informal education to participants, project organisers, and to early and experienced researchers in the area of citizen science and community science. This could be, for example, a course or a class for students about citizen science and/or an activity with visitors to a museum during the summer holidays.

In the grant agreement of ECS, the European Citizen Science Academy has several objectives. The first is to achieve a step-change in the uptake of knowledge about designing and utilising citizen science by research and innovation organisations (R&I), such as public libraries, museums, research performing organisations, research funders and research translation organisations. The second is to achieve a robust integration of citizen science within the excellence research pillar of Horizon

Europe, by developing a network of top researchers that use and or are looking to be supported in their use of citizen science as a research methodology. It will do so by providing tailored training to missions, clusters and networks, which are based on identified needs of these stakeholders, and that address high policy goals such as the EU Green Deal and the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). In addition it seeks to connect citizen science educators and trainers across Europe and the world, and provide training for the activities in the ECS project. The Université Paris Cité/Learning Planet institute is leading this effort.

As a first endeavour to establish the ECS Academy, a network of citizen science educators and trainers was established so that the ECS Academy could be endorsed and co-created from the start with citizen science educators and trainers. To create this network, a survey was sent to citizen science educators and trainers, and diverse mailing lists (i.e. listserv), to ask about their training/educational activities with citizen science and their needs in relation to a network and an academy (i.e. what type of services would be useful to them) and how they would be willing to engage with the ECS Academy. This report elaborates on the answers received.

Methodology

Survey design

The survey was structured into distinct sections to identify the profile of citizen science educators and trainers, to identify their citizen science training/educational activities, characterise these, and understand their needs in terms of a network and an academy, and also more widely, at a European level. This survey was developed from

November 2022 to March 2023. The survey was piloted alongside email templates that addressed individual educators and trainers and mailing lists, from January to February 2023. Piloting the survey with email templates allowed us to fine tune the standard email invitation and the survey to ensure that it was understood by the target audience.

Individuals corresponding to the definition given to citizen science educators and trainers were identified (for example, people who developed a MOOC on citizen science), alongside pertinent listserv in January 2023. These individuals were identified by either being part of an organisation that gave citizen science training, and or by in-house knowledge of Muki Haklay and Cléa Montanari. Secondly, mailing lists such as listserv that were linked to citizen science (ECSA, CSA, Ecology etc.) and national networks were identified (e.g. such as the Citizen Science centre at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel).

The survey was disseminated to these educators and trainers and the relevant listservs on March 16th and it was left open for a month until April 14th. Survey results were downloaded on the 15th April.

Analysis of the survey

Quantitative and qualitative analysis was conducted to analyse the survey responses. In order to group open questions on training, a framework developed by [PATTERN](#) (an EU funded project) was used. This framework elaborated categories for different audiences, training formats, scientific fields, learning resources type. Additional categories were created to fit the data of this survey, such as 'citizen science' as a scientific field.

With regards to open ended questions, an inductive analysis was carried out by the authors of the report. This inductive analysis led respondents' open answers about needs, services, to be regrouped in the following three themes: infrastructure and support, engagement and recognition. Unique statements that pertained to the broader need of European citizen science educators and networks were left apart.

Survey results

Demography of respondents

The survey was answered by 129 individuals. Among them, researchers and academics represented the largest percentage, comprising 59 individuals (48.8%). Research support was the second largest category, with 38 individuals (30.2%). Teachers/trainers accounted for 7 individuals (5.6%), while doctoral/PhD and postdoctoral researchers each comprised 5 individuals (3.9%).

In terms of experience in providing training or teaching in citizen science, 98 respondents (76%), reported having such experience.

With regards to training affiliation, an overwhelming majority of 96 respondents (74%), mentioned that the training they provided was associated with institutions like universities, museums, or research centres.

Citizen science training activity

Type of training

In terms of citizen science training activities, about 47 respondents (36.4%) carried out training/workshops/seminar. 36 respondents (28.6%) gave bachelor/master level courses. 5 respondents (4%) mentioned their citizen science activity to be in relation to research supervision, and an equal number of respondents developed e-learning modules.

Mode of training

Training mode refers to in-person, online and hybrid. This means that training types could be of different modes. The most common format, which comprised of 49 respondents (38.9%) was hybrid (i.e. in-person and online). In-person training was the second most popular format, selected by 36 respondents (28.6%). 7 respondents (5.6%) reported their activities to be carried out online.

Scientific field

Citizen science activities were found in a broad range of academic fields, which included citizen science itself (see recently published book ‘Science of Citizen Science’¹). 42 respondents (32.8%) indicated actively providing training in the field of citizen science, such as history of citizen science, case analysis, co-creation, citizen science related to plastic waste etc. 33 respondents (25.6%) mentioned conducting citizen science training in regards to Environmental Studies, such as for water management and biodiversity. Graph 1 demonstrates the scientific fields represented alongside the number of respondents carrying out a citizen science activity in that field.

Graph 1. Citizen science activities represented in scientific fields.

Target audience

37 respondents (29%) indicated their training to be aimed at students (i.e. both bachelor and master students). 18 respondents (14%) indicated researchers and academics to be the target audience of their citizen science training activity. The 15 respondents’ (12%) training focused on volunteers and community members. 13 respondents (10%) provided training to individuals who were both students and professionals.

¹ Vohland, K., Land-Zandstra, A., Ceccaroni, L., Lemmens, R., Perelló, J., Ponti, M., ... & Wagenknecht, K. (2021). *The science of citizen science* (p. 529). Springer Nature.

Services

The survey asked what services could facilitate present and future training and teaching in citizen science. Respondents could choose multiple answers.

Out of 7 different types of services, open access training material in an editable format that can be translated into different languages emerged as the most desirable service, with 91 (70.5%) respondents. This was followed by an access to a network of citizen science educators and trainers from 87 (67.4%) respondents and the need for a training material directory and repository by 84 respondents (65%).

79 respondents (61%) indicated an interest in modular educational resources that can be easily reused in different contexts. 60 respondents (46.5%) indicated an interest for an announcement service for different citizen science education and training opportunities. Graph 2 summarises respondents' interest to the 7 proposed services.

Graph 2. Services helpful to citizen science educators and trainers.

In addition, three open questions allowed the respondents to elaborate on ideas of services that could be useful or facilitate citizen science training activities, at the individual and at the European level. Respondents' elaboration on useful services have been put into three themes. The first one, ‘Infrastructure & Support’ includes services that pertain to online tools such as a platform, portals and or ‘spaces’, and or resources such as trainings, repositories. The second category, ‘Engagement’ includes for example the need of sharing best

practices between citizen science educators and trainers. The third category 'Recognition' includes for example, the need for awareness raising and

support of citizen science in higher education institutions, and training accreditation of both citizen science trainers and educators and participant

Infrastructure & support

- A portal to advertise bids and calls for citizen science training and teaching.
- A platform where citizen science training could be offered to get in touch with potential participants.
- A space to ask legal questions about citizen science projects to students, such as the Emmett Environmental Law & Policy Clinic at Harvard Law School.
- Guidance on a moment-to-moment and practical level (e.g. to immediately be able to contact someone with questions when something goes wrong).
- A repository of training material with a clear subject matter, goal and audience, so that the wheel is not reinvented, but that expertise is shared and efforts streamlined.
- Access to accessible training, so that these can be adapted, translated, jointly elaborated and uptaken.
- Resources on how to design workshops, which methods to use for different types of projects, skills in presentation, skills in and access to software for online course design, skills in and access to software for web design, skills in events booking and management skills and software access, skills in health and safety (risk assessment) and software access.
- A team to help with organisational aspects of training.
- Tools for student supervision such as a collection of thesis and dissertations on citizen science topics. A directory of contact to speak about relevant topics and advanced international training with personal experience.
- Funding for training and proposal development for joint funding by the European Citizen Science Association (ECSA) involving members through higher education affiliated entities.
- Technological support to stay in contact with people.
- Feedback & evaluation on training/participation.
- Access to quantitative data (for scientific disciplines such as meteorology and climatology).
- A common fund to invite network experts to workshops.
- Resources such as cheap smart mobile phones and or appropriate testing kits and equipment. These are positive for engagement.

Engagement

- Engaging in citizen science projects outside of one's own field.
- Encounters between approaches and trainers with different backgrounds.
- The sharing of best practices and tools in teaching citizen science.

Recognition

- A need to raise awareness of citizen science towards higher education institutions to inform training needs.
- Citizen science branded and recognised as a valuable practice that requires well-considered methods and dedicated training at universities..

- A need for international ethics cafés and workshops for an exchange of expertise, knowledge and skills.
- More lawyers and legal scholars engaged in citizen science.

- Have stronger visibility and inclusion of courses within universities/higher education institutions, and their promotion.
- Certification of trainers of a certain organisation and of participants.
- Broader engagement of non-academic institutions in citizen science.

In addition, few more services were highlighted, unique to the question of what respondents thought *European* citizen science trainers and educators need to thrive.

“The pure engagement of citizens to thrive for a better quality of life, combined with a set of didactic and knowledge skills.”

- Services for citizen science educators and trainers at the European level**
- More widespread knowledge of the strategic importance of citizen science at the community level.
 - Access to insurance for running events and courses.
 - The need to demonstrate citizen science value to and network with young people.
 - Connect with NGOs striving for environmental/societal improvements.
 - Introduce citizen science to schools by the direct involvement of motivated teachers or professional educators.
 - More connections to existing participatory social science activities.
 - National coordination.

Contribution

Amongst the respondents, the majority (i.e. 90 respondents, 69.8%) expressed their willingness to contribute by responding to questions, share experiences, and provide expertise in citizen science training. In addition, 61 respondents (47.3%) indicated that they are willing to grant access to their own training materials and organise and facilitate network activities. 55 respondents (42.6%) indicated an interest in co-facilitating trainers workshops, and 49 respondents (38%) showed interest in developing training materials based on identified needs for the network. Graph 3 reports the number of respondents willing to contribute in various ways.

Graph 3. Preferred mode of contribution by respondents.

In addition to the above mentioned way of contributing, individuals highlighted that in order to share training material they would need to know if their training were of the ‘right kind’ and that they would be more willing to contribute training material if there was a well organised initiative on developing materials, which depended on subject matter and audience.

Respondents also highlighted the willingness to contribute but the lack of time to do so, and or the trickiness of not being based in Europe.

“I am interested in being part of the network and sharing my experience. Unfortunately my biggest constraint is the lack of time, that's why I haven't ticked any other possibilities to get involved for the moment.”

“I would also be happy to contribute in more ways, although the time difference with the West Coast of Canada can be a challenge!”

Finally, one respondent highlighted that they were not planning to teach citizen science but that they were interested in engaging with the ECS Academy to help from a pedagogical point of view to design citizen science training with experts.

Mode of engagement

Respondents could choose between multiple options on the way they would like to be engaged.

90 respondents (69.8%) highlighted they would prefer to be engaged via a newsletter. This was followed by stories and experiences by 51 respondents (39.5%) and a closed listserv by 47 respondents (36.4%). Online meet-ups/calls and open listservs also received significant interest, from 46 respondents (35.7%). Graph 4 highlights all suggested modes to stay engaged with the ECS Academy and respondents' preferred modalities.

Graph 4. Communication modes to stay engaged with ECS Academy.

In addition, respondents were asked at which frequency they would prefer to receive their chosen mode to stay engaged. The preferred frequency matched the preferred mode of communication, a newsletter on a monthly basis.

Individuals which preferred mailing lists, highlighted a preference to stick to existing mailing lists within the citizen science community.

In addition, respondents shared preferences on what they would like the newsletter to contain. New initiatives, programmes and/or training opportunities were mentioned. A respondent suggested a shared calendar between the network of citizen science educators and trainers where different organisations can upload their training, webinars, talks etc. A respondent suggested that the academic calendar is taken into account (e.g. for example August, a month where many university teachers are updating course material).

Some respondents highlighted that they do not want to get overwhelmed by communication from the citizen science network of educators and trainers and therefore would prefer occasional announcements of relevant resources or research.

On a similar note, a respondent highlighted the feeling of being overwhelmed by the 'amount' of information that needs to be processed on a daily basis. Therefore, they hoped this network information to be well-structured and resourceful instead of being overwhelming.

Limitations

The questionnaire had a limitation regarding the implementation of question logic in the google form. As none of the questions were obligatory, some questions that were meant to show only if the respondent had answered 'yes' showed when no answer was given to the question. For example, the participants were asked if they have or are giving training and teaching in citizen science and if the answer was yes, then to specify below. Some respondents didn't select either yes or no, but were able and specified their training.

In addition, the number of services were broad, and one respondent mentioned that they were unsure about what was meant with what type of services citizen science trainers and educators would need in order to thrive, whether it would allow them to find more ways to do training and or be trained. The notion of services may have been ambiguous as the services could come from two sources, the ECS Academy and the network of educators and trainers themselves.

Kick-off event

110 respondents of 129 said they would be interested to be re-contacted to stay engaged in the creation of the European Citizen Science Academy (Graph 5. depicts the result). A kick-off event with these 110 individuals was organised on June 1st. Out of the 110 respondents, the event was attended by 80 respondents.

Graph 5. Number of respondents that wanted to be re-contacted to co-create the ECS Academy.

Next steps

The European Citizen Science Academy is a four year endeavour with the ambition to co-create it with a network of citizen science educators and trainers. The 110 respondents mentioned to be interested to stay engaged in the creation of the ECS Academy set the basis of this network.

During the kick-off event, the results of the survey were presented alongside a working document, called the 'Roadmap to the European Citizen Science Academy' that provides the first iteration and skeletal document for the development of the guidance document for the ECS Academy.

Respondents were invited to share comments in the form of direct suggestions, comments in a google doc, or by email to iterate the introduction, input, vision, stakeholders and target groups, learning framework, operational principles, services offered by the ECS Academy, logic model that set the basis of the ECS Academy. In addition, on the 21st of June 2023, a meeting was organised, to collaboratively work on this Roadmap. A total of 25 respondents attended it, and provided suggestions to each section, and to missing sections of the roadmap, such as "Risks and Mitigations" and "Business plan". This roadmap will be continually elaborated by respondents that will eventually form and shape a network of citizen science educators and trainers, alongside the ECS consortium, ECSA members and ECSA.

A third workshop will soon be organised with interested respondents to elaborate on how and which services will be offered by the ECS Academy. If you want to get involved with the network of educators and trainers, and or have any comments about the report please contact Cléa Montanari at (clea.montanari@learningplanetinstitute.org).